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Solving the international financial crisis and immoral sex problems

Various solutions have been proposed in every age to prevent financial collapse and despite the implementation of efforts to control it, no significant results can be achieved.

Today we are going to describe a basic solution that will help any country's financial stability and could help in sexism prevention.

Governments of different countries pay a huge amount of money every year to support orphaned children. In addition to this, various NGOs collect donations from investors and the public. Which are very huge amounts.

Instead of passing a large amount of money every year in the budget for the care of forbidden children, orphans; the money should be spend on legal action against the miscreants. It could be possible with the help of modern devices. The action should be taken against those who pushed innocents and unawares towards the sexual criminal

offenses. By taking legal action against the crime offenders before committing the crime it could help in reforming economy, moral values, and peoples' thinking.

Modern Technology: The **Mind-reader** technology was allowed in 2007 to the developers at software companies for development. Offered by various companies like NeuroSky, Emotive, Muse, Neurocity, OpenBCI, Odeonus LLC etc.

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With the use of this technology, not only thoughts that lead to debauchery and debauchery from one mind to another can be stopped, but girls and boys can be saved when they move towards sex.

Immoral Activities: Those who dress in immoral and immoral activities in homes, offices, schools, colleges, universities instead of giving attention to education and instead of work, And home-alone boys, girls and elderly people who are the target or cause of sexism can be stopped before they fall into evil using this technology.

In this way, the country's economy will improve and the country's money can be saved from being wasted. Our governments should try to prevent debauchery from occurring.

In this way, a large capital of the country and the nation will be avoided. The moral values of the nation will also improve.

Tags:

#Internationalfinancialcrisis #Preventfinancialcollapse #Financialstabilitysolutions #Endingsexism
#Orphanedchildrensupport #Governmentbudgetallocation #NGOdonations #Moderntechnologyincrimeprevention
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